

Seasonal Evaluation of Nutritive Status of *Cymbopogon jwarancusa* (Jones) Schult Growing Wild in Churu District of Rajasthan

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Abstract The study focuses on the nutritional status of *Cymbopogon jwarancusa* (Jones) Schult. (Poaceae) in various seasons (2021-22). This important perennial herb found in Churu and was assessed for its nutritive contents in the roots, stems, and leaves using the AOAC (1995) method. The findings revealed that the plant is rich in nutrients. During the rainy season, ash, silica, and ether extract were observed in the highest amounts, while dry matter, organic matter, and total carbohydrates were found in the lowest amounts. In contrast, the winter season showed maximum levels of dry matter, organic matter, total carbohydrates, acid detergent fibres, crude proteins, and cellulose, with minimum levels of ash, silica, crude protein, ether extract, neutral detergent fibres, and hemicellulose. Additionally, the winter season exhibited high levels of neutral detergent fibres, hemicellulose, and lignin (leaf), and low levels of acid detergent fibres, cellulose, and lignin (root). The study concludes that this herb is a valuable source of nutrients, suitable for human and livestock consumption.

Keywords Nutritive Contents, Seasonal Evaluation, *Cymbopogon Jwarancusa*, Crude Proteins.

Introduction The natural environment contains various types of untamed vegetation such as herbs, shrubs, and grasses, which are utilized as sources of nourishment for both humans and animals. Plants found in dry and semi-dry regions are valuable reservoirs of phytochemically significant compounds. The Churu district is situated in the central part of North-East Rajasthan, positioned between 28° 18' North Latitude and 74° 58' East Longitude. It is also recognized as "The Gateway to Thar," experiencing minimal precipitation and extreme temperatures. During summer, the temperature rises above 50° C, while in winter, it drops to freezing levels. The climate in Churu is characterized by extreme temperature fluctuations. The annual precipitation in the study area varies from 260-440 millimetres (10-17 inches). *Cymbopogon jwarancusa* (Jones) Schult, locally known as Bur or Buraro, is an upright, perennial, hairless herb with numerous 30 to 150 cm long stems. The leaves are elongated, and the plant bears flowers in clusters. It blooms and produces fruit from August to December.

Objective of study The current study assessed the nutritional content of the root, stem, and leaf of the selected plant species.

Review of Literature *Cymbopogon jwarancusa* (Poaceae) is an important medicinal herb found as a wild throughout India. The name *Cymbopogon* is composed of two Greek words "Kymbe+Pogon". The *Kymbe* meaning a boat and *pogon* a beard, the first one refers to the boat shaped spatheoles and awns that one conspicuous feature of the inflorescences. The species name *jwarancusa* has been composed of two Sanskrit words "Jwar & Ankusha" meaning "Fever and breaker" respectively that recalls the much contained medicinal property allied with the herb. According to Kirtikar and Basu (1982), *Cymbopogon jwarancusa* is utilized for treating various ailments such as vomiting, abdominal tumors, unconsciousness, blood impurities, and skin issues. S. Mohammed, P.K. Kasera, and J.K. Shukla (2004) conducted a study on unexplored plants with potential medicinal properties in the Indian Thar desert, highlighting the usefulness of *Cymbopogon jwarancusa* roots in managing fever, root oil in combating microbial infections and skin diseases, and leaves in the production of soaps and perfumes. The mineral content of certain herbal plant species in the Churu district was assessed by

Kapoor and Gaur (2006). Gul Bano et al. (2009) demonstrated the seasonal variation in the nutritive components (P, N, Ca, Mg, K, and Na) of *Cymbopogon jwarancusa* (Jones) Schult and *Chrysopogon aucheri* in Balochistan. Baga Ram and N. S. Bains (2014) disclosed the nutritive contents of two plant species growing in western Rajasthan. Ravi Parihar and Rohitashv Choudhary (2017) investigated the nutritive status of *Mollugo cerviana* Ser. growing wild in Bikaner District of Rajasthan. Manasi Rajendra.Navale et.al. (2022) studied that Seasonal variations in the nutritive value of fifteen multipurpose fodder tree species the fifteen different MPTs of the mid-hills north-western Himalayan ecosystem in the proximate and mineral compositions, cell wall constituents, anti-nutrient content, and palatability, which are also influenced by the seasonal effect. *Cymbopogon jwarancusa* contains an essential oil rich in piperine that is used as a diaphoretic for gout, chronic rheumatism, and intermittent fever. It is commonly found in sandy or fine gravelly soils, wastelands, and as a weed in cultivated fields, particularly in arid regions. The plant is collected from the wild for local consumption as both a food and a medicinal resource. It is a prevalent plant in Churu and arid-semiarid regions of Rajasthan, and in addition to its medicinal significance, it may contain adequate nutrient levels to be considered as both food and animal fodder. The current study assessed the nutritional content of the root, stem, and leaf of the selected plant species.

Methodology

The roots, stems, and leaves of *Cymbopogon jwarancusa* (Jones) Schult, which were well-developed and free from disease, were gathered from Pirer village and the nearby tehsil headquarters of Sardarshahar in Churu district (2021-22). After collection, each part was dried separately at 100° C for 15 minutes and then at 60° C until a specific weight was reached. Following the drying process, the samples were ground into powder using 20 mesh screens in the Willey mill and subsequently utilized for assessing their nutritional contents using the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC, 1995) Method.

Statistics Used in the Study

Result and Discussion

The nutritive composition of *Cymbopogon jwarancusa* (Jones) Schult was analysed based on the dry matter percentage. The stem had the highest dry matter content at 98.08% in the winter season, while the lowest was in the leaf at 96.36% during the rainy season. In the rainy season, the leaf part of the plant had the highest ash content at 8.79%, whereas the stem had the lowest at 2.09% in the winter. The maximum organic matter at 97.91% was found in the stem during winter, and the minimum at 91.21% was in the leaves during the rainy season. Silica content was highest at 5.63% in the leaf during the rainy season and lowest at 1.02% in the stem during the winter season. The leaf had the highest crude protein at 0.70%, while the stem had the lowest at 0.22% during the winter season. Mathur and Sundaramoorthy S. (2006) reported that the root and stem parts of *Blepharis sindica* had the highest protein contents during the winter season. P.lal.et. al. (2014) observed that the highest crude protein values were in the seedling stage, and the lowest was in the late season. The leaf had the highest ether extract at 3.87% during the rainy season, and the root had the lowest at 0.40% in the winter season. The total carbohydrate value was highest at 96.57% in the stem during winter and lowest at 86.72% in the leaf during the rainy season. The stem had the highest neutral detergent fiber at 79.74% during summer and the lowest at 76.67% in the root during the winter season. The highest acid detergent fibre at 75.77% was reported in the stem during winter, and the lowest at 46.90% in the leaf during the summer season. The leaf had the highest hemicellulose at 31.84% during summer, and the stem had the lowest at 3.20% during the winter season. Lignin was highest at 6.06% in the stem and lowest at 3.49% in the root during the summer season. Cellulose was highest at 70.04% in the stem during the winter season and lowest at 40.84% in the leaf during the summer season. Karamat Mahmud et.al. (2002) provided a biochemical analysis and trace element analysis of *Cymbopogon jwarancusa*. It was found to have 67.02% moisture content, 9.52% ash content, 1.8% carbohydrates, 1.07% reducing sugar, 0.80% non-reducing sugar, 0.67% nitrogen, 5.02% crude proteins, and 9.50% crude fiber. B.B.S Kapoor et.al. (2007) evaluated the mineral contents of medicinal plants in the Hanumangarh district of Rajasthan. Kedia S. et. al. (2008) studied the phytochemical analysis of *Phyllanthus fraternus* during different seasons and growth stages in the Indian arid zone. Various plant species from the research area were analysed for their nutritive properties and found to be a potential source of nutrients. Similarly, *Cymbopogon jwarancusa* is rich in nutrients and can be used as a source of food and fodder for living organisms.

Table: Seasonal Evaluation of Nutritive Status of *Cymbopogon jwarancusa* (Jones) Schult (% of dry matter basis):

S.N.	Seasons	Plant Part	DM (%)	Ash (%)	OM (%)	Silica (%)	CP (%)	EE (%)	TCHO (%)	NDF (%)	ADF (%)	HC (%)	Lignin (%)	Cellulose (%)
1.	Rainy	Root	97.59	7.16	92.84	5.63	0.49	0.41	91.94	79.46	67.57	11.89	4.89	62.68
		Leaf	96.36	8.79	91.21	4.20	0.62	3.87	86.72	77.15	64.85	12.30	5.77	59.08
2.	Winter	Root	97.50	4.53	95.47	3.10	0.43	0.40	94.64	76.67	72.58	4.09	3.99	68.59
		Stem	98.08	2.09	97.91	1.02	0.22	1.12	96.57	78.97	75.77	3.20	5.73	70.04
		Leaf	97.66	6.21	93.89	3.42	0.70	1.25	91.84	78.91	54.07	24.84	4.56	49.51
3.	Summer	Root	97.33	5.39	94.61	4.03	0.35	0.41	93.85	79.71	62.39	17.32	3.49	58.90
		Stem	96.80	3.11	96.89	1.35	0.26	0.71	95.92	79.74	66.40	13.34	6.06	60.67
		Leaf	96.77	5.95	94.05	2.67	0.57	3.30	90.18	78.74	46.90	31.84	5.73	40.84

Abbreviations: (DM= Dry Matter, OM= Organic Matter, CP= Crude Protein, EE= Ether Extract, TCHO= Total Carbohydrates, NDF= Neutral Detergent Fibre, ADF= Acid Detergent Fibre, HC= Hemicellulose)

Conclusion

The study demonstrates that *Cymbopogon jwarancusa* (Jones) Schult, found in the Churu district of Rajasthan as a wild herb, contains adequate nutritional components. As a result, this plant species could potentially serve as food for humans and as fodder for livestock.

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